

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF KNITTED FABRIC REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the structure-property relationships of knitted glass fiber fabric reinforced polypropylene composites. Composites were anisotropic with superior tensile properties in wale direction than in course direction. Tensile properties increased with increasing stitch density of knitted fabric. This was attributed to the increase in fiber content with increasing stitch density. Damage resistance was determined using static compression and drop tower impact tests. Damage resistance parameters: peak load and puncture energy increased with increasing stitch density of knitted fabric, number of plies and imposed strain rate. It is possible to improve the mechanical properties of knitted fabric composites by further increasing the fiber content.

INTRODUCTION

Knitted fabrics are gaining importance in the polymer composite industry owing to their potential for net-shape-manufacture of fiber preforms, and for the excellent drapeability of knitted fabric prepregs [1-3]. Knitted fabrics are made by interloping of fiber yarns. It is a common thought that knitted fabric composites possess lower mechanical properties than conventional laminated composites owing to their curved fiber architecture. Rudd *et al.* [4] have shown that tensile properties of plain weft knitted glass fiber/polyester laminates were comparable to continuous strand mat (CSM) composites. Later, Ramakrishna and Hull [5, 6] improved the tensile properties by inserting straight fibers into the knit loops. Chou *et al.* [7] reported that fatigue properties of weft knitted glass fiber/epoxy laminates were comparable to those of woven fabric reinforced laminates. All the above mentioned work on knitted fabric composites has been carried out using thermoset matrices. Recently, Mayer *et al.* [8], Ramakrishna *et al.* [9] and Kager-Kocsis *et al.* [10] successfully fabricated knitted fabric reinforced thermoplastic composites. Considerable advantages such as cost reduction and process simplification can be achieved by using a combination of co-knitted fiber preforms and compression molding technique. One of the objectives of the present work is to investigate the tensile properties of knitted glass fiber fabric reinforced polypropylene composites.

The knitted fabric reinforced thermoplastic composites are promising candidates for damage tolerant applications in automobile, appliance and medical fields. Hence, in this work we also investigated the damage resistance of knitted glass fiber fabric reinforced polypropylene composites under static compression and low velocity impact conditions.

MATERIALS

Co-knitted fabrics with plain weft knit structure were produced using a flat bed knitting machine at Kyoto Institute of Technology (Kyoto, Japan). Schematic diagram of a plain weft co-knitted fabric is shown in Figure 1. Co-knitted fabrics were made by simultaneous knitting of glass

fiber yarns and polypropylene (PP) fiber yarns. Knitted fabrics with stitch densities 5, 11 and 17 were produced by varying the stitch size selector on the knitting machine. Stitch density is defined as the number of knit loops per square centimeter of the knitted fabric. Higher stitch density means smaller knit loops and more fibers per unit area of the knitted fabric. Knitted fabrics with higher stitch density were stiffer than the knitted fabrics with lower stitch density.

Thermoplastic composite laminates were fabricated by compression molding technique. During compression molding the PP fibers melt and impregnate the knitted fabrics. Laminates of 4 and 16 plies were fabricated. The 4 ply laminates were made using compression molding conditions: 225°C, 6 MPa and 15 minutes. The 16 ply laminates were made using compression molding conditions: 225°C, 15 MPa and 30 minutes. At the end of impregnation, the complete set-up was cooled in air to room temperature. 4 and 16 ply laminates were approximately 1.3 mm and 2.5 mm thick, respectively. The fiber contents of the laminates were determined by combustion method. Variation of fiber content with stitch density is shown in Figure 2. As expected the fiber content increased with increasing stitch density of the knitted fabrics. Void content of the laminates varied in the range from 0.07 to 0.14. Specimens of 90 mm square were cut from the 4 and 16 ply laminates to study the damage resistance. Tensile specimens were prepared from the 4 ply laminates only. Tensile specimens, 200 mm long and 30 mm wide, were cut parallel to the course and wale directions of the knitted fabric. Tensile specimens cut parallel to the course direction of the knitted fabric were referred as 'course specimens' and those cut parallel to the wale direction were referred as 'wale specimens'.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of a plain weft co-knitted fabric.

Figure 2. Variation of fiber content of laminates with stitch density.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

TENSILE TESTS

Tensile tests were conducted using an Instron testing machine at a cross-head speed of 1 mm/min. Load and cross-head displacement were recorded using an x-y recorder. Stress and strain were calculated from the load and cross-head displacement respectively.

DAMAGE RESISTANCE STUDIES

Damage resistance of knitted fabric composites was determined under static compression and low velocity impact conditions using 90 mm square specimens.

Static compression tests were carried out using an Instron model 1125 testing machine. Each specimen was clamped on a cylindrical jig with an internal diameter of 65 mm. The jig was mounted on the fixed cross-head of the testing machine. The same jig was also used in the drop tower impact tests. A tup with 12.7 mm diameter hemispherical nose was mounted on the moving head of the Instron machine. All the specimens were compression tested at a constant cross-head speed of 0.77 mm/minute (0.05 inch/minute). Load-deflection traces were recorded using a computerized data acquisition system.

Low velocity impact tests were conducted using a modified Dynatup model 8200 drop weight impact tower. The instrumented drop tower permits direct measurement of the transient contact force through a 50 kN load transducer located between the cross-head and 12.7 mm diameter hemispherical tup nose. Impact tests were conducted at 4 m/s. The total unloaded weight of the cross-head and the tup was 3625 gm. The drop tower was connected to a GRC model 730-I data acquisition system which records both the transient contact force and the quantity of kinetic energy transferred as a function of time during the impact event.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

TENSILE STUDIES

Typical tensile stress-strain curves for the wale and course specimens are shown in Figure 3. A small initial portion of the stress-strain curves was linear. With further increase of stress, gradual decrease in the slope of the stress-strain curve was observed. Identification of a well defined knee point was difficult. The slope of the course stress-strain curve decreased more rapidly than that of the wale stress-strain curve. The slope of the initial linear portion of the stress-strain curves was calculated as the initial elastic modulus. The failure strains of knitted fabric reinforced composites were as high as 8%, much higher than the 3% failure strain of woven glass cloth/epoxy laminates. Their high failure strains make knitted fabric prepregs suitable for deep drawing and diaphragm forming techniques. Using such prepregs, components with complicated shapes can be fabricated.

The maximum recorded stress was taken as the tensile strength. Variations of elastic modulus and tensile strength with stitch density are shown in Figures 4 and 5, respectively. Tensile properties of both the wale and course specimens increased with increasing stitch density. This increase in tensile properties may be attributed to the fact that the fiber contents of laminates increase with increase of stitch density. The wale specimens displayed higher tensile properties than the course specimens due to the higher amount of fibers oriented in the wale direction of the knit loop.

Figure 3. Typical tensile stress-strain curves for 4 ply knitted fabric composite.

Figure 4. Variation of elastic modulus of 4 ply knitted fabric composite with stitch density.

Figure 5. Variation of tensile strength of 4 ply knitted fabric composite with stitch density.

DAMAGE RESISTANCE STUDIES

Typical load-deflection curves obtained from static compression testing of laminates are shown in Figure 6. In 4 ply laminates the load increased gradually with increasing deflection, whereas in 16 ply laminates the load increased rapidly with increasing deflection. This can be understood by examining the deformation process of the knitted fabric composite.

The knitted fabric alone is not very rigid due to its looped fiber architecture. Even for small external loads, with the absence of surrounding matrix resin, a knitted fabric deforms by changing its knit loop structure. The thermoplastic polypropylene matrix is less rigid compared to thermoset matrices like epoxy and vinylester resins. Effectively we have a composite of a ductile matrix reinforced with highly deformable knitted fabric. However, in the composite, the polypropylene matrix surrounding the knit loops does not allow the knit structure to deform freely. The restrictive support of the matrix resin to knitted fabric makes the composite as a whole fairly rigid. Since the fiber contents of 4 ply laminates were smaller than those of 16 ply laminates, it is possible that effectively the behavior of 4 ply laminates was dominated by the thermoplastic polypropylene matrix. Hence, during initial stages the deformation of 4 ply laminates was large for a small compression load. In the case of 16 ply laminates the fiber contents were sufficiently high, resulting in more resistance to the advancing tup and a rapid increase of compression load.

Figure 6. Typical load-deflection curves obtained from the static compression tests.

After the initial non-linear behavior the compression load increased almost linearly with deflection. At the peak load, material fracture noises were audible. These noises were associated with fracture of fiber bundles in the top plies close to the tup nose. In some cases, no single well defined maximum load was observed, instead a number of peaks were observed in the load-deflection curves. With further advancement of the tup, the load dropped rapidly. The puncture of plies by the tup was also observed. A photograph of the punctured knitted fabric composite laminate is shown in Figure 7. After the hemispherical nose of the tup completely puncture through all the plies, the load gradually stabilized. With further advancement of tup, the load remained constant. The load corresponding to the horizontal asymptotic portion of the load-deflection curve may be attributed to the frictional forces developed between the tup and the punctured specimen.

Our objective is to determine the energy required for puncturing of knitted fabric composite laminates. Hence, the area under the asymptotic portion of the load-deflection curve was not considered. The rest of the area under the load-deflection curve was taken as the puncture energy. Both the peak load and puncture energy were sensitive to the stitch density and number

of plies of knitted fabric (Figures 8 and 9). As expected the 16 ply laminates displayed higher peak loads and puncture energies than the 4 ply laminates. Both peak load and puncture energy increased with increasing stitch density. But the stitch density effect was more obvious in 16 ply laminates. Tensile studies indicated that the stiffness of the knitted fabric composites increases with increasing stitch density (Figure 4). Stiffer composite specimens offer more resistance to the advancement of the tup. Also the number of fiber bundles to be broken increases with increase of stitch density. Hence, with increasing stitch density both peak load and puncture energy increased.

Figure 7. Photograph of static compression tested knitted fabric composite.

Figure 8. Variation of peak load with stitch density.

Figure 9. Variation of puncture energy with stitch density.

A typical load-time trace obtained from impact testing is shown in Figure 10. The load increases with specimen deflection as kinetic energy is transferred from the impactor cross-head to the specimen. Absorbed energy was computed from the load, tup velocity and time information and plotted as energy-time trace in Figure 10. After an initial non-linear behavior the energy increased rapidly with time. At the end of rapid increase, the slope of the energy-time trace decreased. With further increase of time the energy increased linearly. This linear portion of the energy-time trace may be attributed to the frictional energy dissipation. Frictional energy is expected to be constant as there was no changes in the specimen after complete puncture. Since our main interest is to investigate the puncture energy of different material systems, the frictional energy was not deliberated in greater detail. The total energy up to the beginning of linear energy-time curve was taken as the puncture energy.

Figure 10. Typical load and energy versus time curves for impacted knitted fabric composite.

The meaning of peak loads and puncture energies were previously explained. Variations of peak load and puncture energy obtained from impact tests are also summarized in Figures 8 and 9 respectively. Similar to the static test results, both the peak load and puncture energy were sensitive to the stitch density and the number of plies. This implies that peak load and puncture energies are closely interrelated and give a good measure of damage resistance of knitted fabric composites. In general, composites displayed higher peak loads and puncture energies under impact conditions than static test conditions. This may be attributed to the strain rate sensitivity of the knitted fabric reinforced thermoplastic composite materials. Under impact conditions, highest peak load of 3.7 kN and puncture energy of 35 Joules were displayed by the 16 ply laminate with 30.9% weight fraction of fibers. Both the static and impact tests give good measures of damage resistance of composite materials.

CONCLUSIONS

Glass fiber knitted fabric reinforced polypropylene composites were anisotropic. They displayed superior properties in the wale direction than in the course direction. Both the elastic modulus and tensile strength increased with increasing stitch density of knitted fabric.

Both static and impact response of knitted fabric composites showed similar trends. Damage resistance of knitted fabric composites can be measured by two parameters: peak load and puncture energy. Identical composites displayed higher peak load and puncture energy under impact testing conditions compared to static testing conditions. Damage resistance increased with increasing knitted fabric stitch density and number of plies of knitted fabrics. The composites with fiber content 30.9% by weight displayed highest peak load of 3.7 kN and puncture energy of 35 Joules. With further increase of fiber content it is possible to improve the mechanical properties of the knitted fabric composites.

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